

RESEARCH ON CULTIVATING “BELT AND ROAD” FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMPOUND TALENTS BASED ON DIVERSIFIED CBI TEACHING MODE

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Abstract. “Belt and Road” major economic strategic conception is a major instruction made by General Secretary Xi Jinping to accelerate the development of China’s economy and drive a new round of comprehensive opening to the outside world and make a major instruction. The concept of “Belt and Road” mainly focuses on promoting the economic development of relevant cities and regions through cultural exchanges. Under this development trend, foreign language talents have become important strategic resources for regional exchanges and economic cooperation, and their responsibilities and missions cannot be ignored. Therefore, at the current stage of college English teaching reform, training “Belt and Road” foreign language compound talents is the need of social development and the inevitable trend of The Times. Therefore, this paper will deeply discuss the reform of college English teaching under the CBI teaching concept, and how to cultivate “Belt and Road” foreign language compound talents through diversified CBI teaching mode.

Key words: diversified CBI teaching mode, Belt and Road, foreign language compound talent.

Annotatsiya. “Kamar va yo'l” asosiy iqtisodiy strategik kontseptsiyasi Bosh kotib Si Jinping tomonidan Xitoy iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishni jadallashtirish va tashqi dunyoga keng qamrovli ochilishning yangi bosqichini olib borish va katta ko'rsatma berish bo'yicha asosiy ko'rsatma. “Kamar va yo'l” kontseptsiyasi asosan madaniy almashinuv orqali tegishli shahar va mintaqalarning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga ko'maklashishga qaratilgan. Ushbu rivojlanish tendentsiyasi sharoitida chet tili iste'dodlari mintaqaviy almashinuv va iqtisodiy hamkorlik uchun muhim strategik resursga aylandi va ularning majburiyatlari va vazifalarini e'tiborsiz qoldirib bo'lmaydi. Shuning uchun kollejda ingliz tilini o'qitish isloh qilish, “Kamar va yo'l” chet tili aralash iste'dodlarini tayyorlashning hozirgi bosqichida ijtimoiy rivojlanish zarurati va The Times ning muqarrar tendentsiyasidir. Shuning uchun, ushbu maqola CBI o'qitish kontseptsiyasi ostida kollejda ingliz tilini o'qitish islohotini va turli xil CBI o'qitish rejimi orqali “Kamar va yo'l” chet tili murakkab iste'dodlarini qanday rivojlantirish kerakligini chuqur muhokama qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'p qirrali CBI o'qitish rejimi, “Kamar va yo'l”, chet tili aralash iste'dodi.

Аннотация. “пояса и дороги” в основном направлена на содействие экономическому развитию соответствующих городов и регионов посредством культурных обменов. В рамках этой тенденции развития иностранные языковые таланты стали важным стратегическим ресурсом для региональных обменов и экономического сотрудничества, и их обязанности и задачи нельзя игнорировать. Таким образом, на нынешнем этапе реформирования преподавания английского языка в колледже подготовка «пояс и путь» иностранных языков комплектующих талантов является необходимостью социального развития и неизбежной тенденцией времени. В этой связи в настоящем

документе будет подробно рассмотрена реформа преподавания английского языка в колледжах в соответствии с концепцией преподавания в КБР, а также вопрос о том, каким образом развивать "пояс и путь" иностранных языков в сочетании талантов с помощью диверсифицированного способа преподавания в КБР.

Ключевые слова: диверсифицированный способ обучения CBI, пояс и дорога, сочетание иностранного языка и таланта.

CBI Teaching Model

1.1 Introduction to the CBI Teaching Model

CBI teaching model represents a groundbreaking milestone in educational development. Immersive teaching was born in Canada in the 1950s, offering a novel approach that surpassed traditional foreign language teaching methods. Students learning languages through this method can fully exercise their autonomy and voluntarily acquire foreign language knowledge. Subsequently, as society evolved and various teaching philosophies merged, educators connected theories from psychology, linguistics, and modern education with the developing immersive teaching approach, further refining it into the current CBI model, which stands for Content-Based Instruction and translates to 'content-based' in Chinese. This model is a teaching approach and strategy based on content, aiming not just at learning linguistic and cultural knowledge but at integrating the target language into the main content to make language acquisition easier. It emphasizes learning through language use, combining language learning with content. The CBI teaching model prioritizes exploration and interest as starting points for learners, enabling them to actively acquire language knowledge. Throughout the learning process, their language skills improve accordingly, and their ability to understand textual content also enhances. Currently, many overseas institutions adopt the CBI teaching model as their primary language teaching method, using it as an effective way to encourage teachers to enhance their teaching abilities and improve traditional teaching methods. In China, with the introduction of CBI teaching concepts and in-depth research and discussion by experts in the field of language teaching, the CBI teaching model has become a theoretical foundation for conducting teaching practices in areas such as 'content-based teaching' and 'knowledge-oriented tutoring.'

1.2 Theoretical foundation of the CBI teaching model

The theoretical foundation of the CBI teaching model is based on communication theory, second language acquisition theory, and constructivism theory. First, communication theory posits that all human activities are related to communication. In daily life, work, and even professional learning and discussions, achieving communication goals requires the use of specific language content. In college English education, evaluations of students' English proficiency have moved beyond traditional testing systems. Current assessments emphasize students' ability to skillfully use English and communicate effectively in various environments. A key indicator of contemporary college students' English learning outcomes is their ability to use English in real-life interactions. This criterion necessitates that students achieve a balance between the tool-like and communicative aspects of language through university English studies. The most effective way to achieve this is by efficiently integrating language learning with specific content. Second, second language acquisition refers to the process of learning any language other than one's native language after acquiring it. Second language acquisition theory primarily explains and analyzes the characteristics, development, and influencing factors of language learners when acquiring a non-native language. To better input a second language, learners should focus more on

understanding the meaning and information of the learning content rather than being constrained by existing learning forms after initial exposure. The CBI teaching method links language learning content to language input triggers for learners, enabling them to acquire relevant linguistic information through repeated practice, thereby effectively facilitating second language acquisition. Third, constructivism theory emphasizes that students acquire knowledge within a broad social and cultural context, mainly through understanding and absorbing classroom content, participating in group discussions with peers during class, and engaging in post-class exchanges. Therefore, creating a positive language learning atmosphere, encouraging active and effective student participation in classroom activities, and achieving efficient language acquisition through actual communication activities are stringent requirements for instructors under constructivism theory.

1.3 Principles to follow when reforming university English teaching using the CBI instructional approach

1.3.1 Principle of language learning content as the core of teaching

Before reforming university English teaching, teachers typically organized classroom instruction by explaining and analyzing language forms and practicing with examples in relevant contexts. At that time, most university English textbooks focused heavily on grammar, with few textbooks organizing scenarios based on the difficulty level of language learning content. The content-based courses in the CBI model are more targeted and comprehensive than traditional courses and require that textbook writing be entirely based on teaching content. Under this model, university English teaching does not intentionally distinguish between language functions and language forms. Classroom instruction primarily involves acquiring language through theme-based and practice-based modes using textbooks consistent with the teaching content, ultimately aiming to improve students' English usage skills.

1.3.2 Principle of using authentic English original materials

Original English textbooks were rarely used in university English teaching before the reform. However, under the CBI instructional approach, university English classes require teachers to use original textbooks. The selected authentic English materials should be as comprehensive and diverse as possible and can also include English songs or videos closely related to the teaching content. Using authentic English materials during lessons is highly practical, and teachers can edit and integrate these materials according to students' actual situations and specific teaching needs. This not only ensures that students' knowledge is promptly updated but also significantly enhances their overall English application abilities.

1.3.3 Comprehensive Training Principle for English Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing, and Translation

Under the CBI teaching concept, college English instruction aims to provide students with integrated training. The specific operational requirements include having instructors organize classroom layouts and guidance centered on content, ensuring that the entire teaching process involves comprehensive language practice from listening, speaking, reading, writing, and translation. This approach better reflects the authenticity of the English learning process, demonstrates the evolution of language development and learning in line with societal progress, and meets the contemporary students' specific needs for improving their overall English communication skills.

1.3.4 Principle of Adapting to Different Students' Specific Needs

During the process of learning English, due to individual differences among students, their understanding, cognition, and application abilities of the language vary. Traditional college

English teaching models are more suitable for students whose end-of-term English scores are above average. It is challenging for these traditional models to fully consider individual differences. Under the CBI teaching model, college English instruction takes into account and appropriately arranges for individual differences among students. Instructors are required to develop several teaching plans based on the varying needs of different students and adjust the applicability of each plan promptly to cater to students at various levels and with different foundations. This 'principle of adapting to different students' specific needs' significantly enhances the enthusiasm and initiative of students at all levels in learning English and helps balance the existing gaps in language learning among students. Therefore, college English instruction under the CBI teaching model is widely welcomed by the student community.

2. Diversified Evaluation and Stratified Teaching

2.1 Limitations of Traditional College English Instruction

Traditional college English instruction primarily categorizes students based on their high school entrance exam English scores into different levels such as basic, intermediate, and advanced classes. Students in advanced classes, due to higher high school English scores, generally have better foundational knowledge. Consequently, teachers set relatively higher teaching goals and conduct lessons accordingly, which naturally improves these students' English proficiency and practical application skills. However, for basic class students with weaker foundations, teachers lower their teaching objectives and follow a corresponding lesson plan. Additionally, these students often lack interest and motivation, leading to negative attitudes towards learning. This stratification approach in traditional college English instruction results in a significant disparity in English performance among students, which can negatively impact the effectiveness of college English education.

2.2 Implementing Diversified Evaluation and Stratified Teaching for College English

2.2.1 Diversified Stratified Teaching Based on Student Profiles

To meet the requirements of diversified teaching evaluations, universities first administer an English test to incoming freshmen, which includes written, listening, and speaking sections. Based on the combined scores from these three parts, freshmen are divided into three levels for university English instruction: Level 3 (total score < 60), Level 2 (total score 60-79), and Level 1 (total score ≥ 80). Due to the increasing demand for versatile foreign language talents, students within each level are further divided into three learning groups—Group A (average listening and speaking scores ≥ 80), Group B (average listening and speaking scores 60-79), and Group C (average listening and speaking scores < 60)—based on their previous test results. To further motivate and engage students in learning English, the existing stratified teaching is continuously adjusted and modified after implementing diversified stratified instruction. Comprehensive assessment involves evaluating students based on factors such as attendance, classroom participation, originality of assignments, and final exam scores, recorded in teachers' logs. At the end of each semester, the comprehensive assessment scores serve as the primary basis for adjusting the stratified classes for the next semester. Students may move up from Level 3 to Level 2 or Level 1 due to diligent study, or they might drop from Level 1 to Level 2 or Level 3 if they neglect their studies. Such adjustments can occur at any time within the different levels and among the A, B, and C groups within each class. This approach ensures that the potential and motivation of students across all levels and within different groups are fully mobilized.

2.2.2 Diversified stratified teaching based on teaching objectives

Firstly, according to diversified stratification, set and adjust the teaching objectives for third-level class students. For third-level class students with weaker English foundations, the teaching objectives should focus on training their basic English skills in the first two semesters. Starting from the third semester, the emphasis should shift to increasing vocabulary through reading, aiming for the ability to read medium-length articles independently. In the fourth semester, teachers should guide students to strengthen their listening and speaking skills, equipping them with basic English communication abilities.

Secondly, according to diversified stratification, set and adjust the teaching objectives for second-level class students. The English proficiency of second-level class students is between good and poor, so the teaching objectives should prioritize solidifying their foundational English knowledge. After completing this task, the objectives can be adjusted to enhance the English communicative competence of second-level class students. Two semesters of foundational courses can be offered, starting from the third semester to develop the English application and communicative abilities of second-level class students. Teaching methods can be flexibly adjusted to include common activities such as watching celebrity interview videos and retelling, English proficiency test lectures, and English corners; from the fourth semester, teachers should encourage students to create more opportunities for oral exchanges with international students and increase writing practice to improve their English application skills.

3. Conclusion

In the process of college English teaching, while enriching and improving their own language professional skills, teachers should also break through the traditional teaching concepts and teaching models. By attempting to introduce the CBI teaching model into the reform of college English teaching and constantly combining diversified evaluation with stratified teaching, they can get closer and closer to the goal of cultivating compound foreign language talents under the background of the "Belt and Road Initiative".

REFERENCES

1. Dai Qingning, Lyu Ye. CBI Teaching Philosophy and Teaching Mode (J). Foreign Language Teaching, 2011, (06)
2. He Yutao. Analysis of the Demand for Foreign Language Talents in Regional Economic Development (J). Northern Economics and Trade, 2012, (02)
3. Li Li. Research on the Effectiveness of Integrating CBI Teaching Concepts into Business English Teaching (J): Beijing International Studies University (08)
4. Zhai Rui. Analysis of the Diversified Stratified Teaching Evaluation Model of College Public English (J) Journal of Changchun Normal University
5. Xie Yajun. Design of Business English Teaching Process Based on CBI Teaching Concept (J) Journal of Hunan University of Commerce, 2
6. Yuan Pinghua, Yu Liming Research on Content-based College English Teaching Mode (J). Foreign Language Teaching and Research
7. Zhang Liping. Implications of CBI Concept for Advanced English Teaching in English Majors of Normal Universities (J) Jilin Radio and Television, 2011, (07)
8. Wang Chuming College English Teaching Reform from the Perspective of Foreign Language Learning (J). Foreign Language Teaching and Research, 2004, (06).
9. Wen Qiufang. The Application of Output-Driven Hypothesis in College English Teaching: Thoughts and Suggestions (J). Foreign Language Journal, 2013, (06).

10. Wang Shixian On the Cognitive Theoretical Basis of CBI (J). *Foreign Languages and Foreign Language Teaching*, 1994, (05)
11. Chang Junyue An Empirical Study on the Teaching Issues Based on the Content of the Basic Stage of English Major (J). *Foreign Language and Foreign Language Teaching*, 2008, (12)
12. Shu Dingfang, Zhuang Zhixiang *Modern Foreign Language Teaching: Theory, Practice and Method* (M). Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press, 2008.
13. Wen Qiufang. The Changing characteristics and trends of Motivation, Concepts and Strategies of English Learners (J). *Foreign Language Teaching and Research*, 2001, (02)
14. Sun Youzhong *English Education and General Education in Humanities: Lecture Series on the Development of Humanities at Tsinghua University, Part Four* (J) *Foreign Language Teaching and Research*, 2010, (04)
15. Hu Wenzhong On the Cultivation of English Professionals in China: Review and Prospect (J). *Foreign Language Teaching and Research*, 2008, (05)
16. Department of Higher Education, Ministry of Education *Teaching Requirements for College English Course (Trial)*(M). Beijing: Tsinghua University Press, 2004.
17. Yuan Pinghua. The Basis and Practice of Foreign Language Teaching Based on Curriculum Content (J). *Foreign Languages and Foreign Language Teaching*, 2006, (08)
18. CAI Jigang ESP and the Development Direction of College English Teaching in China (J). *Foreign Language Journal*, 2004, (02)